

Rewiring Receptor Activation: Mechanistic Insights into Toggle Switch Modulation by 25CN-NBx Compounds

Vito F. Palmisano,^{*,†,‡} Micaela Vidal-Sánchez,[†] and Juan J. Nogueira^{*,†,¶}

[†]*Department of Chemistry, Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain.*

[‡]*International Foundation Big Data and Artificial Intelligence for Human Development, Bologna, Italy*

[¶]*IADCHEM, Institute for Advanced Research in Chemistry, Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain*

E-mail: vito.palmisano@ifabfoundation.org; juan.nogueira@uam.es

Abstract

The development of new treatments for neuropsychiatric disorders relies on a deeper understanding of the molecular mechanisms behind psychedelic compounds, particularly how they differentiate between hallucinogenic and antidepressant effects. In this study, we explore by molecular dynamics simulations a series of 25CN-NBx compounds bound to the 5-HT_{2A} receptor. The simulations uncover that bulky substitutions on the N-benzyl ring cause a significant shift in the position of W336, a key toggle switch residue known to influence receptor activation and thought to play a crucial role in mediating psychedelic signaling. This result is confirmed through potential of mean force calculations along the toggle switch's dihedral angle. End-state free energy calculations align closely with experimental data, showing that 25CN-NB-2-OH-3-Me and

25CN-NB-2-OH-5-MeO have the highest and lowest affinities, respectively, for the 5-HT_{2A} receptor. Further analysis indicates that when W336 adopts its negative dihedral state, it establishes stronger van der Waals interactions, stabilizing its contacts with residues F332 and I163 — key players previously linked to receptor activation. Our findings provide a framework for understanding receptor activation and can be extended to other G protein-coupled receptors where the toggle switch is central to signal activation.

Introduction

One of the central questions in the neuropsychopharmacology of psychedelic compounds is whether the acute hallucinatory effects can be separated from the rapid and long-lasting antidepressant effects at the downstream signaling level.¹ This question drives current research efforts towards understanding the role of the 5-hydroxytryptamine 2A receptor (5-HT_{2A}R), which is known to mediate both hallucinatory and antidepressant effects,²⁻⁵ although recent findings also suggest that neural plasticity could be promoted independently of the 5-HT_{2A}R.⁶ Serotonergic psychedelics, derived from various chemotypes (e.g., tryptamines, phenethylamines, and ergotamines), activate the 5-HT_{2A}R with different potency and efficacy.⁷ Indeed, 5-HT_{2A}R agonists typically activate both the G_{q/11} pathway^{8,9} and β -arrestin2 translocation,^{10,11} with most of them exhibiting similar activation profiles to the balanced endogenous agonist 5-HT or serotonin.¹² Recent advances in the structure-based discovery of 5-HT_{2A}R have led to the development of compounds that act as biased agonists, capable of stabilizing the receptor in conformations that preferentially favor one downstream signaling pathway over the other.¹³ Kaplan et al.,¹⁴ through virtual screening of several million molecules, identified two compounds that produced antidepressant-like effects in mice without hallucinogenic properties, showing a bias towards G_{q/11} activation over β -arrestin2 recruitment. In contrast, Wang et al.¹⁵ identified two other compounds that retained antidepressant-like effects in mice without inducing a hallucinogenic response and showed a bias towards β -arrestin2 signaling. In this latter case, a high transduction

efficiency of 5-HT_{2A}R agonists in both G_{q/11} and β -arrestin2 recruitment was required to induce hallucinogenic effects, while a low transduction efficiency of 5-HT_{2A}R β -arrestin2 bias was sufficient to achieve antidepressant-like effects.

While developing new chemotypes targeting the 5-HT_{2A}R, recent years have seen significant advancements in the structure-activity relationships of compounds derived from mescaline (Figure 1A) and 2,5-Dimethoxy-4-iodoamphetamine (DOI) (Figure 1B).^{7,16} Notably, the incorporation of an N-benzyl group at the ethylamine domain has led to the synthesis of a class of compounds with remarkable affinity and potency for the 5-HT_{2A}R.^{17,18}

Figure 1: Chemical structure of (A) mescaline, (B) DOI, (C) 25CN-NBOH, (D) 25CN-NB, (E) 25CN-NB-2-OH-3-Me, (F) 25CN-NB-2-OH-5-MeO, (G) 25CN-N1-Nap, (H) 25CN-NBPh, (I) 25CN-NDBF.

Among these DOI derivatives, 25CN-NBOH (**1**) (Figure 1C) exhibits high binding affinity for the 5-HT_{2A}R, with significantly lower affinity for the other two subtypes, 5-HT_{2B}R and 5-HT_{2C}R.^{19–21} Recently, (**1**) was crystallized bound to the 5-HT_{2A}R, revealing a new binding

pose compared to the crystallized structure of the 5-HT_{2A}R bound to LSD. In this pose, the 2-OH group is inserted deeply into the orthosteric binding pocket, interacting with a novel region of the receptor between helices TM3 and TM6 and forming key interactions with the indole ring of W336 (Figure 2A).¹⁰ This residue, known as the "toggle switch", has been proposed to control G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) activation during signal transduction,²² and a comparison with other 5-HTRs bound to other chemotypes reveals that the crystallized structure of the 5-HT_{2A}R bound to **(1)** displays the largest change in displacement of W336.^{23,24}

Figure 2: Representation of a portion of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor (orange) highlighting W336 to illustrate the transition from (A) a positive value of the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle when interacting with 25CN-NBOH (**1**), where the indole core of the residue points towards the extracellular medium, to (B) a negative value of the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle when interacting with 25CN-N1-Nap (**5**), where the indole core of the residue points towards the intracellular medium.

In 2023, Wallach et al.¹² conducted a study on various 25N-NBx compounds, demonstrating that the addition of bulky groups results in a substantial reduction in 5-HT_{2A}R G_{q/11} efficacy while preserving 5-HT_{2A}R β -arrestin2 efficacy. In addition, it was shown that changes in the electron density at the N-benzyl ring highly influence the 5-HT_{2A}R affinity (Figure 1D-F). Induced fit molecular docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of these bulky compounds, 25CN-N1-Nap (**5**) (Figure 1G) and 25CN-NBPh (**6**) (Figure 1H), show a substantial change in the displacement of the χ_2 dihedral angle of W336 ($\chi_2(\text{W336})$) from positive to negative values, driving the indole core of the residue towards the inner

side of the 5-HT_{2A}R (Figure 2). These β -arrestin2 biased compounds demonstrated a lack of hallucinogenic potential, and a comprehensive assay of 25N-NBx derivatives revealed that when G_{q/11} activation exceeds 70% efficacy, hallucinogenic effects are observed in mice. In contrast, β -arrestin2 activation alone, as seen with 25N-NBx compounds containing bulky substituents, does not appear to be sufficient to induce such effects. A correlation emerges between the weak G_{q/11} activation and the negative values of χ_2 (W336), highlighting the importance of developing a computational protocol capable of predicting the most stable orientation of toggle switch upon N-benzyl additions to the 25CN-NBx compounds.

To this end, in this computational study, we applied MD simulations in combination with umbrella sampling (US) and molecular mechanics generalized Born surface area (MMGBSA) free energy calculations to obtain the potential of mean force (PMF) along the χ_2 (W336) upon different N-benzyl additions for a set of 25CN-NBx compounds (Figure 1C-I). Given that during unbiased MD simulations of some compounds, W336 transitioned from its initial state with χ_2 (W336) = 60°, as in the 5-HT_{2A}R-(**1**) complex, to a state where the indole core pointed deep into the receptor, corresponding to negative values of χ_2 (W336), we used US to obtain the PMF along the χ_2 (W336) and identify the local minima for each compound. The identified minima were correlated with the G_q efficacy data reported by Wallach et al., demonstrating that the addition of bulky substituents to the N-benzyl group stabilizes the toggle switch in conformations with negative χ_2 (W336) values. In this orientation, where the indole core of W336 points toward the intracellular side of the receptor, the residue establishes strong van der Waals interactions with I163 and F332—two residues previously implicated in a conserved motif that undergoes conformational changes during receptor activation.²⁵ These findings offer insight into how allosteric changes are propagated within the active state of the 5-HT_{2A}R, and highlight a transferable strategy for studying other GPCRs in which the TM6 toggle switch plays a central role in receptor activation.

Results and Discussion

Molecular Dynamics Simulations: Spontaneous Toggle Switch Rotation

To validate the stability of (1)-(7) inside the orthosteric binding pocket, four independent replicas of 1 μ s production run were conducted for each compound. The RMSD of the ligands with respect to the aligned 5-HT_{2A}R shows that all the compounds remained tightly bound in the orthosteric binding pocket maintaining the initial pose throughout the full 4 μ s simulation with an average value of approximately 1.5 Å (Figure 3).

Figure 3: RMSD of (1)-(7) with respect to the non hydrogen atoms of the aligned 5-HT_{2A} receptor for the 4 μ s of MD simulations.

Figure 4: Distribution of the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle along the 4 μs of cMD simulation for (1)-(7)

Interestingly, during the dynamics of (3), (4), (5), (6), and 25CN-NDBF (7), the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle naturally jumped from its initial value of approximately $60\text{-}80^\circ$ to negative values of approximately -20° (Figure 4). Given that in the apo-structure $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ exhibits a value of approximately 100° , with its indole core oriented toward the extracellular domain,²⁵ and shifts to around 60° in the crystal structure bound to (1), we chose to use $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ as a reaction coordinate for US simulations to obtain a converged PMF and identify the most stable conformation for each of the psychedelic compounds. The goal is to find a relationship between the ligand structure and the binding pose, especially regarding the W336 orientation and its potential role in the activation of a particular biological route.

Identification of Two Toggle Switch Conformations by Umbrella Sampling Simulations

The US simulations validated that the addition of N-benzyl substituents, particularly bulky substituents as in **(5)**, **(6)**, and **(7)**, forces the toggle switch W336 to orient its indole core towards the inner part of the receptor, with negative $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ values (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Potential of mean force (PMF) along the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle for **(1)**-**(7)**.

Starting from **(1)** (Figure 5A), we begin our comparison with **(2)**, **(3)**, and **(4)** to observe the effect of -2-OH, -2-OH-3-Me, and -2-OH-5-MeO additions to the ring (Figure 5B-D). In **(1)** and **(2)**, only one evident minimum is present at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 60^\circ$, with a small change in the PMF upon -2-OH addition at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -20^\circ$. Instead, the addition of -2-OH-3-Me in **(3)** induces a pronounced formation of a second minimum at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -20^\circ$, 11 kcal/mol

higher in energy than the minimum displayed at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 60^\circ$. Finally, the addition of -2-OH-5-MeO in compound **(4)** induces a substantial change in the PMF, pushing the minimum at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -20^\circ$ at the same energy as $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 60^\circ$. Indeed, both -2-OH-3-Me and -2-OH-5-MeO additions show experimentally a reduced $G_{q/11}$ efficacy, indicating that this reduction in activity can be well correlated with the negative $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ values and the indole core of the toggle switch projected towards the inner side of the receptor.¹²

As highlighted earlier, Wallach et al., motivated by the observed reduction in $G_{q/11}$ efficacy upon C_3' addition, further explored various substituents on the N-benzyl ring, increasing the bulk on the side of the molecule that extends toward an unexplored region of the orthosteric binding pocket. The PMFs from the US simulations for **(5)**, **(6)**, and a newly synthesized compound, **(7)**, all of which exhibited low $G_{q/11}$ efficacy,^{12,26} show minima at negative $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ values. The **(5)** species (Figure 5E) exhibits two clear minima, with the deepest one at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 100^\circ$, and the other at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -15^\circ$, with a minor energy difference of 2 kcal/mol. Conversely, **(6)** (Figure 5F) displays the deepest minimum at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -30^\circ$ and the other at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 60^\circ$, which is 6 kcal/mol higher in energy. Finally, 25CN-NDBF **(7)** (Figure 5G) presents a clearly different scenario with one minimum at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 100^\circ$, similar to 25CN-N1-Nap **(5)**, but located 16 kcal/mol higher in energy than the global minimum at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$. The binding of **(7)** also demonstrated that a dibenzofuran addition is well tolerated in the inner side of the 5-HT_{2A}R, indicating that large bulky substituents are well accommodated in that region of the 5-HT_{2A}R. The US simulations provide a reliable tool for precisely estimating the conformational changes of the toggle switch W336 and can be extended to study other GPCR receptors.

Binding Free Energy Calculations

N-Benzyl Polar Substituents Addition

The crystallized structure of 5-HT_{2A}R bound to **(1)** reveals a hydrogen bond between the -2-OH substituent and polar residues in TM3 of the 5-HT_{2A}R,¹⁰ which has been suggested

to contribute to its increased affinity.^{10,27} Therefore, we decided to compare the binding affinity of the unsubstituted N-benzyl compound **(2)** with the -2-OH compound **(1)**, as well as with two compounds that were experimentally found to have the highest and lowest affinity for the 5-HT_{2A}R, respectively, **(3)** and **(4)**.¹² Our results confirm that compound **(3)**

Table 1: Binding free energy (ΔG_{tot}) of **(1)**-**(4)**/ 5-HT_{2A}R and decomposition into ligand/receptor van der Waals (ΔG_{vdw}) and electrostatic (ΔG_{el}) interactions, and complex/solvent polar (ΔG_{polar}) and non polar (ΔG_{np}) interactions in kcal/mol.

compounds	ΔG_{vdw}	ΔG_{el}	ΔG_{pol}	ΔG_{np}	ΔG_{tot}
25CN-NBOH (1)	-53.7	-106.3	98.2	-6.8	-68.6
25CN-NB (2)	-54.9	-116.7	111.3	-6.7	-67.0
25CN-NB-2-OH-3-Me (3)	-60.7	-109.4	106.4	-7.1	-70.9
25CN-NB-2-OH-5-MeO (4)	-55.8	-107.9	109.5	-7.0	-61.3

exhibits the highest ΔG_{tot} , followed by **(1)** and **(2)**, while **(4)** shows the lowest ΔG_{tot} , with a difference of 9.6 kcal/mol compared to the highest affinity compound. The primary factor that differentiates the binding of **(3)** is its more favorable ΔG_{vdw} , suggesting that the -3-Me addition stabilizes certain hydrophobic interactions within the orthosteric binding pocket. The other three compounds exhibit very similar ΔG_{vdw} values, indicating that the -2-OH and -5-MeO additions do not significantly affect the hydrophobic interactions within the pocket. Notably, all three additions in **(1)**, **(3)**, and **(4)** result in a substantial reduction in ΔG_{el} , compared to the unsubstituted compound **(2)**, which has a difference of -10 kcal/mol in its favor. This indicates that these additions alter the drug’s binding pose, reducing favorable electrostatic interactions with the protein while enhancing hydrophobic interactions. The polar solvation energy is highest for compound **(2)** (111.3 kcal/mol), which is somewhat unexpected given that it lacks polar substituents such as hydroxyl or methoxy groups. In contrast, compound **(4)**, which contains both -2-OH and -5-OMe groups and is expected to form extensive hydrogen bonding with water, shows a slightly lower polar solvation energy (109.5 kcal/mol). This suggests that, upon binding to the receptor, some interactions with the solvent may be partially retained, particularly in compounds bearing polar substituents. Compound **(1)** exhibits the lowest polar solvation penalty (98.2 kcal/mol), indicating that

its interaction with the aqueous environment might be partially maintained even in the bound state, possibly due to the orientation of the -2-OH group. The solvation penalty for compound **(3)** (106.4 kcal/mol) also reflects a moderate retention of solvent interactions. These findings suggest that the desolvation process may not be complete upon receptor binding, and that polar groups might continue to engage with water molecules or polar residues in the binding pocket. The non-polar contribution to the solvation energy, ΔG_{np} , remains similar across all compounds and appears to play a less discriminating role in the observed differences.

Figure 6: Pairwise residue decomposition of the binding free energy for (1)-(7). Each residue contribution is in turn decomposed into ligand/protein van der Waals (vdw) and electrostatic (el) contributions and polar (pol) and nonpolar (np) solvation contributions to the total residue binding energy (tot).

Each binding energy term was further pairwise decomposed into ligand-residue binding free energies (Figure 6). First, comparing these results to the crystal structure in Kim et al.,¹⁰ we observed that all the major interactions are retained in **(1)**. In TM3, D155 is the major contributor to the binding energy, creating a salt bridge with the tertiary amine of the ligand, while V156 and S159 create alkyl- π and hydrogen bonding interactions, respectively, followed by interactions with the hydrophobic cage in TM6 and TM7 formed by W336, F339, F340, G369, and T370. Interestingly, **(1)**, **(3)**, and **(4)** display a slightly lower ΔG_{el} at S159 compared to **(2)**, indicating that the hydrogen bond at this position may actually compete with the salt bridge at D155 and decrease the overall electrostatics.

The 2-OH-3-Me addition in **(3)** appears to induce an overall decrease in ΔG_{vdw} , which is distributed among all the major residue interactions. Along with compound **(4)**, it also shows the strongest interactions with the toggle switch W336. These results confirm that C₃ addition increases the affinity for the 5-HT_{2A}R, primarily due to an increase in electron density at the N-benzyl ring, which better accommodates within the hydrophobic cage.

N-benzyl Bulky Substituents Addition

The addition of bulky substituents, as in **(5)**, **(6)**, and **(7)**, induces an increase in ΔG_{vdw} , with **(7)** displaying the highest increase, which is mirrored in the highest ΔG_{tot} (Table 2). The electrostatic interactions are more favorable for **(6)**, but it also incurs the highest ΔG_{pol}

Table 2: Binding free energy (ΔG_{tot}) of **(5)**-**(7)** to the 5-HT_{2A}R inside the orthosteric binding pocket and decomposition into ligand/receptor van der Waals (ΔG_{vdw}) and electrostatic (ΔG_{el}) interactions, and complex/solvent polar (ΔG_{polar}) and non polar (ΔG_{np}) interactions in kcal/mol.

compounds	ΔG_{vdw}	ΔG_{el}	ΔG_{pol}	ΔG_{np}	ΔG_{tot}
25CN-N1-Nap (5)	-63.6	-103.4	102.3	-7.3	-72.2
25CN-NBPh (6)	-62.4	-104.8	108.1	-7.4	-67.0
25CN-NDBF (7)	-67.9	-101.7	102.1	-7.9	-75.5

penalty, which is 6 kcal/mol higher compared to the other two compounds, resulting in the least favorable ΔG_{pol} . The pairwise ligand-residue free energy decomposition reveals

relatively similar interactions among the three compounds. However, for **(7)**, the ΔG_{vdw} values are more favorable and evenly distributed among the residues in the pocket, attributed to the dibenzofuran substituent, which penetrates deeper into the inner part of the 5-HT_{2A}R. In addition to interactions within the hydrophobic cage of TM6, primarily involving W336, F339, and F340, these interactions extend to residues in TM7, particularly V366, G369, and Y370 (Figure 6), and also include alkyl- π interactions with I163, a key residue implicated in a conserved motif known to undergo conformational changes upon receptor activation.²⁵

Binding Free Energy Associated with the Toggle Switch

To further investigate the driving forces behind the formation of the two distinct minima observed in the US simulations, we performed an MMGBSA analysis, treating the toggle switch W336 as the ligand and the rest of the protein along with compound **(7)** as the receptor. The geometries for the free energy calculations were extracted at equidistant intervals from the 50 ns simulations corresponding to the two US windows where the free-energy minima were identified. We specifically focused on the US simulation of compound **(7)**, as it presented the largest energy difference between the two minima. This approach allowed us to compute ΔG_{tot} between W336 and the rest of the system, and decompose it into pairwise interactions to identify the key components responsible for its stabilization. The major energy difference is observed in the ΔG_{vdw} , which favors the global minimum at

Table 3: Binding free energy (ΔG_{tot}) of W336 at $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ at -5° and 95° inside the orthosteric binding pocket and decomposition into ligand/receptor van der Waals (ΔG_{vdw}) and electrostatic (ΔG_{el}) interactions, and complex/solvent polar (ΔG_{pol}) and polar (ΔG_{np}) interactions in kcal/mol.

25CN-NDBF (7)	ΔG_{vdw}	ΔG_{el}	ΔG_{pol}	ΔG_{np}	ΔG_{tot}
$\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$	-61.2	-29.6	21.1	-3.9	-69.0
$\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 95^\circ$	-55.4	-27.1	22.0	-4.0	-60.0

$\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$, resulting in a more favorable ΔG_{tot} . Both ΔG_{el} and ΔG_{pol} also favor the global minimum, while ΔG_{np} remains unchanged between the two conformations.

Figure 7: (A) Pairwise residue decomposition of the binding free energy for W336. Each residue contribution is in turn decomposed into ligand/protein van der Waals (vdw) and electrostatic (el) contributions and polar (pol) and nonpolar (np) solvation contributions to the total residue binding energy (tot). (B) Time evolution of the χ_2 dihedral angle of F332 (yellow) and W336 (blue) during the umbrella sampling window at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$ (pink) and the umbrella sampling window at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 95^\circ$ (light blue).

Pairwise binding free energy decomposition identifies F332 as the major contributor to the stabilization of W336 in both conformations at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$ and $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 95^\circ$, with a slightly stronger ΔG_{vdW} for the latter (Figure 7A). Visual inspection of the 50 ns of MD simulation in both $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$ and $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 95^\circ$ US windows displays interesting behavior of F332 (Figure 7B). In the window corresponding to $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = -5^\circ$ the $\chi_2(\text{F332})$ is stabilized in a conformation at approximately -30° , while in the window corresponding to the US window at $\chi_2(\text{W336}) = 95^\circ$ a large change in displacement is observed for $\chi_2(\text{F332})$, shifting to 180° . In addition, in both minima, the toggle switch interacts with I163 primarily

through ΔG_{vdw} interactions, but no clear conformational changes in this residue were observed during the dynamics. Both F332 and I163 have been implicated as part of a motif explaining how allosteric changes are transmitted down the receptor,^{25,28} and these results underscore the importance of these residues and quantify their interactions with the toggle switch.

Conclusions

Determining which 5-HT_{2A}R downstream signaling pathway is responsible for the hallucinatory effects of psychedelic compounds is essential for developing new treatments for neuropsychiatric disorders. Recent studies on a series of 25CN-NBx derivatives have revealed a direct correlation between hallucinatory effects in mice and the level of G_{q/11} pathway activation, with compounds exceeding 70% G_{q/11} efficacy consistently inducing psychedelic-like behaviors. This pathway activation has also been closely associated with conformational changes in the toggle switch W336. In this work, we demonstrate through a combination of unbiased and US MD simulations, together with MMGBSA calculations, that the stability and conformational changes of the toggle switch W336 can be predicted and tuned with different N-benzyl substitutions on 25CN-NBx compounds. Unbiased MD simulations indicate that W336 can naturally adopt two distinct conformations depending on the N-benzyl additions of the ligands, with the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ serving as the key reaction coordinate relevant to this conformational change. Consequently, we employed US to sample $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ from -60° to 120° and found that the addition of bulky substituents to the N-benzyl group shifts the minimum energy of $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ to negative values, causing the indole core of W336 to orient toward the intracellular region of the 5-HT_{2A}R. Indeed, the PMFs for **(5)**, **(6)**, and **(7)**, all of which exhibited low G_{q/11} efficacy and lacked hallucinogenic effects, showed a pronounced minimum at negative $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ values, confirming a correlation between reduced G_{q/11} signaling and the inward displacement of the toggle switch. The MMGBSA results align with

experimental findings, showing that the addition of a -2-OH-3-Me group in compound **(3)** significantly enhances its affinity for the 5-HT_{2A}R, whereas the -2-OH-5-MeO substitution in compound **(4)** results in the lowest affinity. The methyl group at the C_{3'} position appears to increase the electron density and promote a tighter fit within the hydrophobic regions of the binding pocket, leading to more favorable ΔG_{vdw} interactions with surrounding residues. In contrast, the methoxy group at C_{5'} does not enhance ΔG_{el} or ΔG_{vdw} but significantly increases the ΔG_{pol} penalty. The addition of bulky substituents, as in compounds **(5)**, **(6)**, and **(7)**, strengthens the van der Waals interactions overall, reflected by more favorable (i.e., more negative) ΔG_{vdw} values. Finally, we demonstrated that the stability of $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ at negative values is associated with stronger ΔG_{vdw} interactions, where the residue directly interacts with F332, stabilizing it at a distinct $\chi_2(\text{F332})$ conformation, and also forms strong contacts with I163. Both F332 and I163 have been implicated in the allosteric activation of the 5-HT_{2A}R. These findings provide atomic-level insights into how different substituents within the 25CN-NBx class can stabilize specific conformations of the 5-HT_{2A}R, and have broader implications for the study of GPCR activation mechanisms involving the TM6 toggle switch.

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References

- (1) Kwan, A. C.; Olson, D. E.; Preller, K. H.; Roth, B. L. The neural basis of psychedelic action. *Nat. Neurosci.* **2022**, *25*, 1407–1419.

- (2) Ly, C.; Greb, A. C.; Cameron, L. P.; Wong, J. M.; Barragan, E. V.; Wilson, P. C.; Burbach, K. F.; Zarandi, S. S.; Sood, A.; Paddy, M. R.; others Psychedelics promote structural and functional neural plasticity. *Cell Rep.* **2018**, *23*, 3170–3182.
- (3) Olson, D. E. Biochemical mechanisms underlying psychedelic-induced neuroplasticity. *ACS Biochem.* **2022**, *61*, 127–136.
- (4) Vargas, M. V.; Dunlap, L. E.; Dong, C.; Carter, S. J.; Tombari, R. J.; Jami, S. A.; Cameron, L. P.; Patel, S. D.; Hennessey, J. J.; Saeger, H. N.; others Psychedelics promote neuroplasticity through the activation of intracellular 5-HT_{2A} receptors. *Science* **2023**, *379*, 700–706.
- (5) Cameron, L. P.; Patel, S. D.; Vargas, M. V.; Barragan, E. V.; Saeger, H. N.; Warren, H. T.; Chow, W. L.; Gray, J. A.; Olson, D. E. 5-HT_{2A}Rs mediate therapeutic behavioral effects of psychedelic tryptamines. *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* **2023**, *14*, 351–358.
- (6) Moliner, R.; Girych, M.; Brunello, C. A.; Kovaleva, V.; Biojone, C.; Enkavi, G.; Antenucci, L.; Kot, E. F.; Goncharuk, S. A.; Kaurinkoski, K.; others Psychedelics promote plasticity by directly binding to BDNF receptor TrkB. *Nat. Neurosci.* **2023**, *26*, 1032–1041.
- (7) Nichols, D. E. Chemistry and structure–activity relationships of psychedelics. *Behav. Neurobiol. Psychodelic Drugs* **2018**, 1–43.
- (8) Raymond, J. R.; Mukhin, Y. V.; Gelasco, A.; Turner, J.; Collinsworth, G.; Gettys, T. W.; Grewal, J. S.; Garnovskaya, M. N. Multiplicity of mechanisms of serotonin receptor signal transduction. *Pharmacol. Ther.* **2001**, *92*, 179–212.
- (9) Roth, B. L.; Nakaki, T.; Chuang, D.-M.; Costa, E. Aortic recognition sites for serotonin (5HT) are coupled to phospholipase C and modulate phosphatidylinositol turnover. *Neuropharmacol.* **1984**, *23*, 1223–1225.

- (10) Kim, K.; Che, T.; Panova, O.; DiBerto, J. F.; Lyu, J.; Krumm, B. E.; Wacker, D.; Robertson, M. J.; Seven, A. B.; Nichols, D. E. Structure of a hallucinogen-activated Gq-coupled 5-HT_{2A} serotonin receptor. *Cell* **2020**, *182*, 1574–1588.e19.
- (11) Luttrell, L. M.; Lefkowitz, R. J. The role of β -arrestins in the termination and transduction of G-protein-coupled receptor signals. *J. Cell Sci.* **2002**, *115*, 455–465.
- (12) Wallach, J.; Cao, A. B.; Calkins, M. M.; Heim, A. J.; Lanham, J. K.; Bonniwell, E. M.; Hennessey, J. J.; Bock, H. A.; Anderson, E. I.; Sherwood, A. M.; others Identification of 5-HT_{2A} receptor signaling pathways associated with psychedelic potential. *Nat Commun.* **2023**, *14*, 8221.
- (13) Smith, J. S.; Lefkowitz, R. J.; Rajagopal, S. Biased signalling: from simple switches to allosteric microprocessors. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **2018**, *17*, 243–260.
- (14) Kaplan, A. L.; Confair, D. N.; Kim, K.; Barros-Álvarez, X.; Rodriguiz, R. M.; Yang, Y.; Kweon, O. S.; Che, T.; McCorvy, J. D.; Kamber, D. N.; others Bespoke library docking for 5-HT_{2A} receptor agonists with antidepressant activity. *Nature* **2022**, *610*, 582–591.
- (15) Cao, D.; Yu, J.; Wang, H.; Luo, Z.; Liu, X.; He, L.; Qi, J.; Fan, L.; Tang, L.; Chen, Z. Structure-based discovery of nonhallucinogenic psychedelic analogs. *Science* **2022**, *375*, 403–411.
- (16) Shulgin, A. *Psychotropic Agents*; Springer, 1982; pp 3–29.
- (17) Elz, S.; Klass, T. H. R.; Wamke, U.; Pertz, H. H. Development of highly potent partial agonists and chiral antagonists as tools for the study of 5-HT_{2A}-receptor mediated function. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Arch. Pharmacol.* **2002**, *365*, R29.
- (18) Heim, R. Synthese und pharmakologie potenter 5-HT_{2A}-rezeptoragonisten mit N-2-methoxybenzyl-partialstruktur. Ph.D. thesis, Freie Universität Berlin, 2003.

- (19) Hansen, M.; Phonekeo, K.; Paine, J. S.; Leth-Petersen, S.; Begtrup, M.; Brauner-Osborne, H.; Kristensen, J. L. Synthesis and structure–activity relationships of N-benzyl phenethylamines as 5-HT_{2A}/2C agonists. *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* **2014**, *5*, 243–249.
- (20) Fantegrossi, W. E.; Gray, B. W.; Bailey, J. M.; Smith, D. A.; Hansen, M.; Kristensen, J. L. Hallucinogen-like effects of 2-([2-(4-cyano-2, 5-dimethoxyphenyl) ethylamino] methyl) phenol (25CN-NBOH), a novel N-benzylphenethylamine with 100-fold selectivity for 5-HT_{2A} receptors, in mice. *Psychopharmacology* **2015**, *232*, 1039–1047.
- (21) Halberstadt, A. L.; Sindhunata, I. S.; Scheffers, K.; Flynn, A. D.; Sharp, R. F.; Geyer, M. A.; Young, J. W. Effect of 5-HT_{2A} and 5-HT_{2C} receptors on temporal discrimination by mice. *Neuropharmacology* **2016**, *107*, 364–375.
- (22) Shi, L.; Liapakis, G.; Xu, R.; Guarnieri, F.; Ballesteros, J. A.; Javitch, J. A. β 2 adrenergic receptor activation: Modulation of the proline kink in transmembrane 6 by a rotamer toggle switch. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2002**, *277*, 40989–40996.
- (23) García-Nafria, J.; Nehmé, R.; Edwards, P. C.; Tate, C. G. Cryo-EM structure of the serotonin 5-HT_{1B} receptor coupled to heterotrimeric Go. *Nature* **2018**, *558*, 620–623.
- (24) McCorvy, J. D.; Wacker, D.; Wang, S.; Agegnehu, B.; Liu, J.; Lansu, K.; Tribo, A. R.; Olsen, R. H. J.; Che, T.; Jin, J.; others Structural determinants of 5-HT_{2B} receptor activation and biased agonism. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **2018**, *25*, 787–796.
- (25) Wacker, D.; Wang, C.; Katritch, V.; Han, G. W.; Huang, X.-P.; Vardy, E.; McCorvy, J. D.; Jiang, Y.; Chu, M.; Siu, F. Y. Structural features for functional selectivity at serotonin receptors. *Science* **2013**, *340*, 615–619.
- (26) Soares, B. A.; Yempala, T.; Martínez-Afani, D.; Acevedo-Fuentes, W.; Brea, J.; Loza, M. I.; Cimadevila, M.; Cassels, B. K. Effect of Bulky N-Dibenzofuranylmethyl

- Substitution on the 5-HT₂ Receptor Affinity and Efficacy of a Psychedelic Phenethylamine. *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* **2024**,
- (27) Hansen, M.; Jacobsen, S. E.; Plunkett, S.; Liebscher, G. E.; McCorvy, J. D.; Bräuner-Osborne, H.; Kristensen, J. L. Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of N-benzyl substituted 4-bromo-2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines as 5-HT_{2A/2C} partial agonists. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2015**, *23*, 3933–3937.
- (28) Gumper, R. H.; Jain, M. K.; Kim, K.; Sun, R.; Sun, N.; Xu, Z.; DiBerto, J. F.; Krumm, B. E.; Kapolka, N. J.; Kaniskan, H.; others The structural diversity of psychedelic drug actions revealed. *Nat. Commun.* **2025**, *16*, 2734.